

Density and viscosity of binary liquid mixtures of *n*-propylamine with polar and non-polar solvents vis-à-vis molecular interactions

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Density and viscosity of the binary liquid mixtures of *n*-propylamine with polar and non-polar solvents viz. acetone, ethyl alcohol, 1,4-dioxane, carbon tetrachloride, benzene and toluene have been measured at 303.15 K. From density and viscosity data the values of excess molar volume (V^E), the excess viscosity (η^E) and the excess Gibbs free energy of activation of flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) have been determined. The computed results have been fitted to Redlich-Kister polynomial equation. Further, the density and viscosity data have been theoretically analysed for the validity of several viscosity models. The main thrust of the study is to correlate the excess properties and the relevant interaction parameters with the nature of molecular interactions between the mixing components.

Oswal and Rao¹ determined densities and viscosities of the binary liquid mixtures of some tertiary amines with cyclohexane and benzene and computed the values of the thermodynamic excess properties and characteristic parameter d in Grunberg and Nissan equation². Fernandez *et al.*³ determined excess molar enthalpy (H^E) of binary mixtures of benzene with *n*-alkylamines at 303.15 K.

Weng⁴ has recently reported studies on the measurement of densities and viscosities for the binary mixtures of butylamine with aliphatic alcohols (1-butanol, 1-pentanol, 1-hexanol, 1-heptanol and 1-octanol) at 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K. The data have been used to obtain the values of excess molar volume (V^E) and excess viscosity (η^E). Both V^E and η^E have been found to be negative. The experimental values of V^E and η^E have been fitted to Redlich-Kister polynomial equation⁵.

From the above brief survey of literature it appears that comprehensive studies relating to the nature and magnitude of molecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures of *n*-propylamine with polar and non-polar solvents are still lacking. With this aim in view the title study has been undertaken.

Results and discussion

The experimental values of densities and viscosities of the pure components have been compared with the literature values and presented in Table I. It is seen that the experimental values compare fairly well with the literature values.

Table I. Comparison of experimental density (ρ) and viscosity (η) of pure liquids with literature values at 303.15 K

Pure liquid	ρ (g cm ⁻³)		η (mPa.s)	
	Expt.	Lit.	Expt.	Lit.
<i>n</i> -Propylamine	0.7099	0.7173	0.3670	0.3760
Acetone	0.7824	0.7899	0.2975	0.2950
Ethyl alcohol	0.7818	0.7789	1.0036	1.0033
1,4-Dioxane	1.0233	1.0337	1.0224	1.1800
Carbon tetrachloride	1.5775	1.5840	0.8300	0.8430
Benzene	0.8659	0.8765	0.5390	0.5640
Toluene	0.8604	0.8669	0.5229	0.5260

The experimental values of excess viscosity (η^E), excess molar volume (V^E) and excess Gibbs free energy of activation of flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) have been determined⁶ as a function of the composition of binary mixtures and have been presented in Table 2. The results are discussed as below :

It is seen that the values of η^E for the binary mixtures of *n*-propylamine with acetone and carbon tetrachloride are positive over the entire range of composition, while with ethyl alcohol, 1,4-dioxane, benzene and toluene they are negative. The positive values of η^E may be attributed to the presence of strong interactions between the unlike molecules of the binary liquid mixtures⁷. The negative values of η^E may be attributed to the dominance of dispersion forces between the mixing components of the binary liquid mixtures⁸.

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Table 2. Values of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and excess properties (η^E , V^E , $\Delta G^{\#E}$) for binary liquid mixtures of *n*-propylamine with polar and non-polar solvents at 303.15 K

Sl. no.	ϕ_1	x_1	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	η (mPa.s)	η^E (mPa.s)	V (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G^{\#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + acetone system								
1.	0.0	0.0000	0.7824	0.2974	0.0000	74.233	0.0000	0.00
2.	0.1	0.0901	0.7873	0.4109	0.1072	73.889	-1.1579	729.20
3.	0.2	0.1821	0.7890	0.5339	0.2238	73.850	-2.0280	1312.42
4.	0.3	0.2763	0.7910	0.6375	0.3208	73.786	-2.9429	1679.98
5.	0.4	0.3727	0.7920	0.7154	0.3920	73.818	-3.7814	1892.60
6.	0.5	0.4710	0.7850	0.7623	0.4321	74.605	-3.8820	1998.77
7.	0.6	0.5722	0.7764	0.7996	0.4623	75.566	-3.8354	2068.43
8.	0.7	0.6755	0.7640	0.7306	0.3861	76.932	-3.4027	1801.39
9.	0.8	0.7813	0.7490	0.6523	0.3004	78.618	-2.6721	1483.55
10.	0.9	0.8890	0.7350	0.4952	0.1358	80.266	-1.9965	753.02
11.	1.0	1.0000	0.7099	0.3671	0.0000	83.265	0.0000	0.00
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + ethyl alcohol system								
1.	0.0	0.0000	0.7818	1.0036	0.0000	58.928	0.0000	0.00
2.	0.1	0.0729	0.7816	0.9234	-0.0338	60.159	-0.5429	-36.53
3.	0.2	0.1502	0.7814	0.8500	-0.0580	61.465	-1.1188	-62.59
4.	0.3	0.2326	0.7768	0.7763	-0.0793	63.212	-1.3769	-83.47
5.	0.4	0.3204	0.7706	0.7052	-0.0945	65.206	-1.5193	-101.23
6.	0.5	0.4144	0.7629	0.6387	-0.1011	67.471	-1.5422	-108.45
7.	0.6	0.5150	0.7545	0.5807	-0.0951	69.961	-1.5007	-89.71
8.	0.7	0.6230	0.7449	0.5240	-0.0831	72.753	-1.3368	-70.37
9.	0.8	0.7392	0.7328	0.4689	-0.0642	76.022	-0.8958	-46.32
10.	0.9	0.8641	0.7212	0.4168	-0.0368	79.503	-0.4544	-22.57
11.	1.0	1.0000	0.7099	0.3671	0.0000	83.265	0.0000	0.00
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + 1,4-dioxane system								
1.	0.0	0.0000	1.0233	1.0224	0.0000	86.104	0.0000	0.00
2.	0.1	0.1030	0.9946	0.9058	-0.0491	85.585	-0.2262	-45.82
3.	0.2	0.2053	0.9653	0.7720	-0.1159	85.110	-0.4114	-189.97
4.	0.3	0.3069	0.9351	0.6596	-0.1617	84.707	-0.5252	-327.63
5.	0.4	0.4078	0.9039	0.5823	-0.1729	84.394	-0.5521	-382.13
6.	0.5	0.5080	0.8714	0.5326	-0.1569	84.207	-0.4548	-345.44
7.	0.6	0.6079	0.8386	0.4953	-0.1287	84.046	-0.3323	-266.92
8.	0.7	0.7073	0.8059	0.4617	-0.0972	83.879	-0.2168	-183.97
9.	0.8	0.8055	0.7734	0.4272	-0.0674	83.722	-0.0954	-122.63
10.	0.9	0.9031	0.7415	0.4008	-0.0298	83.507	-0.0338	-29.69
11.	1.0	1.0000	0.7099	0.3671	0.0000	83.265	0.0000	0.00
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + carbon tetrachloride system								
1.	0.0	0.0000	1.5775	0.8300	0.0000	97.509	0.0000	0.00
2.	0.1	0.1151	1.4962	0.8167	0.0400	95.521	-0.3481	189.86
3.	0.2	0.2264	1.4176	0.7952	0.0700	93.382	-0.9025	338.67
4.	0.3	0.3340	1.3409	0.7713	0.0959	91.123	-1.6284	464.11
5.	0.4	0.4384	1.2566	0.7435	0.1164	89.367	-1.8970	578.77
6.	0.5	0.5391	1.1703	0.7023	0.1218	87.808	-2.0220	637.86

7.	0.6	0.6375	1.0797	0.6481	0.1132	86.545	-1.8837	640.39
8.	0.7	0.7319	0.9890	0.5855	0.0943	85.442	-1.6423	583.70
9.	0.8	0.8242	0.8944	0.5034	0.0549	84.705	-1.0644	407.60
10.	0.9	0.9130	0.8025	0.4364	0.0290	83.925	-0.5795	242.23
11.	1.0	1.0000	0.7099	0.3671	0.0000	83.265	0.0000	0.00
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + benzene system								
1.	0.0	0.0000	0.8659	0.5390	0.0000	90.207	0.0000	0.00
2.	0.1	0.1073	0.8546	0.5039	-0.0167	89.014	-0.4480	-77.75
3.	0.2	0.2130	0.8402	0.4695	-0.0329	88.149	-0.5789	-156.91
4.	0.3	0.3169	0.8245	0.4366	-0.0479	87.434	-0.5735	-239.03
5.	0.4	0.4192	0.8075	0.4106	-0.0563	86.867	-0.4298	-290.48
6.	0.5	0.5199	0.7887	0.3896	-0.0600	86.512	-0.0859	-315.32
7.	0.6	0.6194	0.7708	0.3813	-0.0512	86.068	-0.1610	-266.15
8.	0.7	0.7164	0.7545	0.3805	-0.0354	85.485	0.2511	-175.10
9.	0.8	0.8123	0.7392	0.3783	-0.0211	84.789	0.2212	-98.12
10.	0.9	0.9069	0.7245	0.3743	-0.0088	84.029	0.1173	-36.95
11.	1.0	1.0000	0.7099	0.3671	0.0000	83.265	0.0000	0.00
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + toluene system								
1.	0.0	0.0000	0.8604	0.5229	0.0000	107.090	0.0000	0.00
2.	0.1	0.1250	0.8428	0.4850	-0.0184	104.427	0.3155	-62.37
3.	0.2	0.2432	0.8250	0.4495	-0.0355	101.948	0.6524	-134.16
4.	0.3	0.3550	0.8056	0.4127	-0.0549	99.819	1.1872	-232.04
5.	0.4	0.4615	0.7900	0.3845	-0.0665	97.338	1.2428	-311.38
6.	0.5	0.5623	0.7765	0.3718	-0.0635	94.742	1.0489	-310.35
7.	0.6	0.6584	0.7641	0.3718	-0.0485	92.125	0.7217	-234.31
8.	0.7	0.7502	0.7515	0.3739	-0.0321	89.635	0.4187	-149.10
9.	0.8	0.8371	0.7384	0.3716	-0.0209	87.338	0.1920	-97.48
10.	0.9	0.9208	0.7241	0.3713	-0.0081	85.245	0.0930	-32.95
11.	1.0	1.0000	0.7099	0.3617	0.0000	83.265	0.0000	0.00

The values of V^E are negative for the binary mixtures of *n*-propylamine with ethyl alcohol, acetone, carbon tetrachloride and 1,4-dioxane over the entire range of composition, while they are positive for the mixtures with toluene. In case of mixtures with benzene, the values of V^E are negative in the benzene rich region but become positive in the *n*-propylamine rich region and that at $x_1 \approx 0.58$, the value $V^E = 0$ (vide Fig. 2). The negative values of V^E may be attributed to the specific interactions between the mixing components, while the positive values of V^E observed in the case of binary mixtures of *n*-propylamine with toluene may be ascribed to the relatively larger size of the toluene molecules which do not pack well with the smaller molecules of *n*-propylamine resulting in the increase of the volume of the mixture. In the case of binary mixtures of *n*-propylamine with benzene the positive values of V^E in the *n*-propylamine rich region, i.e. $x_1 > 0.58$, may be attributed

to dipole-induced dipole interactions⁹.

A perusal of Table 2 shows that the values of $\Delta G^{\#E}$ are positive over the entire range of composition for the binary mixtures of *n*-propylamine with acetone and carbon tetrachloride, while the values are negative for the rest of the mixtures.

Typical plots of η^E , V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ versus x_1 have been presented in Figs. 1, 2 and 3, respectively. The plots are of parabolic shape and are characterized by the presence of minima/maxima, which give the composition at which the maximum interactions are expected to occur⁷.

The excess properties η^E , V^E and $\Delta G^{\#E}$ were fitted to the Redlich-Kister equation of the type :

$$X^E = x_1 x_2 \left[\sum_{i=0}^k A_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \right] \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1. Variation of excess viscosity (η^E) with mole fraction (x_1) at 303.15 K: (O) *n*-propylamine + acetone; (Δ) *n*-propylamine + benzene.

Fig. 3. Variation of excess Gibbs free energy of activation of flow ($\Delta G^{\#E}$) with mole fraction (x_1) at 303.15 K: (Δ) *n*-propylamine + benzene; (O) *n*-propylamine + acetone.

Fig. 2. Variation of excess molar volume (V^E) with mole fraction (x_1) at 303.15 K: (O) *n*-propylamine + acetone; ($\times$) *n*-propylamine + benzene; (Δ) *n*-propylamine + toluene.

where $A_0, A_1, A_2, \dots, A_i$ are the adjustable coefficients evaluated by least-square method¹⁰, using a computer [P-III system]; X^E is $\eta^E/\text{mPa.s}$ or $V^E/\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ or $\Delta G^{\#E}/\text{J mol}^{-1}$. The A_i coefficients are then used to evaluate $X_{\text{cal.}}^E$ values from the eq. (5). The standard deviation $\sigma(X^E)$ is defined by the equation¹¹.

$$\sigma(X^E) = \left[\frac{\sum (X_{\text{obs.}}^E - X_{\text{cal.}}^E)^2}{(n-p)} \right]^{0.5} \quad (6)$$

where n is the number of data points and p is the number of coefficients, A_i . The values of these coefficients along with standard deviation $\sigma(X^E)$, have been evaluated from eqs. (5) and (6). The data have been listed in Table 3. It is seen that the fit is good as shown by the small values of standard deviation.

Viscosity models and interaction parameters :

The viscosities of binary liquid mixtures under discussion have been correlated to the following viscosity models :

Grunberg and Nissan² have suggested the following logarithmic relation between the viscosity of the binary mixture and pure components

$$\ln \eta = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_1 x_2 d_{12} \quad (7)$$

where d_{12} is a constant, the values of d_{12} have been listed in Table 4. It is seen that the values of d_{12} are positive in case of binary liquid mixture of *n*-propylamine with acetone and carbon tetrachloride but are negative with ethyl alcohol, 1,4-dioxane, benzene and toluene. The positive values of d_{12} may be attributed to the presence of strong interactions between the mixing components¹², while the negative values of d_{12} indicate the presence of dispersion forces¹³.

Tamura-Kurata¹⁴ put forward the following equation for the viscosity of binary liquid mixtures

$$\eta = x_1 \phi_1 \eta_1 + x_2 \phi_2 \eta_2 + 2(x_1 x_2 \phi_1 \phi_2)^{0.5} . T_{12} \quad (8)$$

Table 3. Coefficients of Redlich-Kister equation and the standard deviation for the binary mixtures of *n*-propylamine with polar and non-polar solvents at 303.15 K

Functions	A_0	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	$\sigma(F^E)$
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + acetone							
η^E (mPa.s)	1.7972	0.1565	-0.6026				0.0139
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-15.569	-1.664	-0.151				0.1954
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	8107.7	675.0	2486.3	-2708.0	-3459.6	525.1	0.9132
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + ethyl alcohol							
η^E (mPa.s)	-0.3883	0.1145	0.0020				0.0016
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-6069	2.867	-0.231				0.0545
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-380.3	365.7	112.8	-722.5	-65.3	781.3	0.9520
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + 1,4-dioxane							
η^E (mPa.s)	-0.6473	0.2613	0.2615				0.0099
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-1.884	1.626	0.767				0.0233
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-1400.1	1309.5	933.9	-3935	905.2	3113.3	0.2600
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + carbon tetrachloride							
η^E (mPa.s)	0.4844	0.0341	-0.2021				0.0045
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-8.096	-2.230	4.681				0.0624
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	2489.5	1320.5	-271.5	-1926.0	191.7	1495.7	0.0260
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + benzene							
η^E (mPa.s)	-0.2332	0.0401	0.1701				0.0016
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	-0.618	4.533	-1.461				0.0637
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-1247.5	69.8	1732.3	716.1	-1213.3	-762.2	0.0800
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + toluene							
η^E (mPa.s)	-0.2554	0.0228	0.2200				0.0029
V^E (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	4.635	-1.642	-5.139				0.0967
$\Delta G^{#E}$ (J mol ⁻¹)	-1266.3	-34.9	2561.8	-623.5	-2390.8	1240.5	0.2560

Table 4. Values of interaction parameters d_{12} , T_{12} and H_{12} at 303.15 K

Sl. no.	x_1	d_{12}	T_{12}	H_{12}	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + acetone system											
1.	0.0000	0.0000	-	-	0.3204	-0.1407	0.5445	0.4684			
2.	0.0901	3.7118	0.9549	0.9862	0.4144	-0.1448	0.5456	0.4770			
3.	0.1821	3.6712	1.0557	1.0836	0.5150	-0.1168	0.5566	0.4950			
4.	0.2763	3.5222	1.1136	1.1345	0.6230	-0.0992	0.5637	0.5085			
5.	0.3727	3.4188	1.1583	1.1706	0.7392	-0.0910	0.5679	0.5188			
6.	0.4710	3.3797	1.1964	1.1993	0.8641	-0.0826	0.5723	0.5287			
7.	0.5722	3.5482	1.2845	1.2766	1.0000	0.0000	-	-			
8.	0.6755	3.4515	1.2306	1.2130	<i>n</i> -Propylamine + 1,4-dioxane system						
9.	0.7813	3.6339	1.2393	1.2114	1.	0.0000	0.0000	-	-		
10.	0.8890	3.2702	1.0515	1.0205	2.	0.1030	-0.1687	0.4202	0.4290		
11.	1.0000	0.0000	-	-	3.	0.2053	-0.4330	0.3309	0.3397		
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + ethyl alcohol system											
1.	0.0000	0.0000	-	-	4.	0.3069	-0.5826	0.3070	0.3147		
2.	0.0729	-0.1475	0.5342	0.4353	5.	0.4078	-0.6013	0.3305	0.3368		
3.	0.1502	-0.1179	0.5482	0.4582	6.	0.5080	-0.5274	0.3757	0.3809		
4.	0.2326	-0.1282	0.5464	0.4634	7.	0.6079	-0.4283	0.4203	0.4247		
					8.	0.7073	-0.3407	0.4560	0.4600		
					9.	0.8055	-0.3038	0.4765	0.4798		
					10.	0.9031	-0.1305	0.5212	0.5245		

Table-4 (contd.)

11.	1.0000	0.00 0	-	-
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + carbon tetrachloride system				
1.	0.0000	0.0000	-	-
2.	0.1151	0.7633	0.7909	0.7948
3.	0.2264	0.8100	0.7912	0.7984
4.	0.3340	0.8952	0.8041	0.8141
5.	0.4384	1.0056	0.8216	0.8350
6.	0.5391	1.0976	0.8267	0.8437
7.	0.6375	1.1800	0.8223	0.8435
8.	0.7319	1.2645	0.8145	0.8388
9.	0.8242	1.1894	0.7624	0.7881
10.	0.9130	1.2835	0.7542	0.7813
11.	1.0000	0.0000	-	-
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + benzene system				
1.	0.0000	0.0000	-	-
2.	0.0729	-0.1475	0.5342	0.4353
3.	0.1502	-0.1179	0.5482	0.4582
4.	0.2326	-0.1282	0.5464	0.4634
5.	0.3204	-0.1407	0.5445	0.4684
6.	0.4144	-0.1448	0.5456	0.4770
7.	0.5150	-0.1168	0.5566	0.4950
8.	0.6230	-0.0992	0.5637	0.5085
9.	0.7392	-0.0910	0.5679	0.5188
10.	0.8641	-0.0826	0.5723	0.5287
11.	1.0000	0.0000	-	-
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + toluene system				
1.	0.0000	0.0000	-	-
2.	0.1030	-0.1687	0.4202	0.4290
3.	0.2053	-0.4330	0.3309	0.3397
4.	0.3069	-0.5826	0.3070	0.3147
5.	0.4078	-0.6013	0.3305	0.3368
6.	0.5080	-0.5274	0.3757	0.3809
7.	0.6079	-0.4283	0.4203	0.4247
8.	0.7073	-0.3407	0.4560	0.4600
9.	0.8055	-0.3038	0.4765	0.4798
10.	0.9031	-0.1305	0.5212	0.5245
11.	1.0000	0.0000	-	-

where T_{12} is the interaction parameter, ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are the volume fractions of pure component 1 and 2 respectively.

Molecular interactions may also be interpreted by the viscosity model by Hind *et al.*¹⁵.

$$\eta = x_1^2 \eta_1 + x_2^2 \eta_2 + 2x_1 x_2 H_{12} \quad (9)$$

where H_{12} is Hind interaction parameter.

A perusal of the values of T_{12} and H_{12} (Table 4) shows

that they do not differ appreciably from each other. This is in agreement with the view put forward by Fort and Moore¹³ in regard to the nature of parameter T_{12} and H_{12} . It is however, significant to note that the values of T_{12} and H_{12} are larger for the binary mixtures of *n*-propylamine with acetone and carbon tetrachloride, which involve strong molecular interactions as revealed by the positive values of η^E and d_{12} .

McAllister¹⁶, on the basis of Eyring's three body interaction model, has proposed the following equation for the viscosity (η) of binary liquid mixtures :

$$\ln \eta = x_1^3 \ln \eta_1 + 3x_1^2 x_2 \ln Z_{12} + 3x_1 x_2^2 \ln Z_{21} + x_2^3 \ln \eta_2 - \ln (x_1 + x_2 M_2/M_1) + 3x_1^3 x_2 \ln [(2 + M_2/M_1)/3] + 3x_1 x_2^2 \ln [(1 + 2 M_2/M_1)/3] + x_2^3 \ln (M_2/M_1) \quad (10)$$

where Z_{12} and Z_{21} are the McAllister interaction parameters.

Heric and Brewer¹⁷ have proposed the following equation for the kinematic viscosity $\lambda (= \eta/\rho)$ of the binary liquid mixtures.

$$\lambda = x_1 \lambda_1 + x_2 \lambda_2 + x_1 x_2 [a + b(x_1 - x_2) + c(x_1 - x_2)^2] \quad (11)$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 are the kinematic viscosities of component 1 and 2 respectively and a , b and c are the Heric and Brewer interaction parameters.

Table 5. Values of McAllister parameters (Z_{12} and Z_{21}) and Heric and Brewer parameters (a , b , c) at 303.15 K

System	Z_{12}	Z_{21}	$a \times 10^2$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	$b \times 10^2$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	$c \times 10^2$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)
<i>n</i> -Propylamine + Acetone	1.0451	0.3604	2.2010	0.2842	-0.6678
Ethyl alcohol	0.5016	0.2285	-0.4876	0.1953	-0.0298
1,4-Dioxane	0.4737	0.2070	-0.5912	0.2350	0.3195
Carbon tetrachloride	0.8360	0.2687	0.3054	0.1236	-0.0919
Benzene	0.3773	0.1383	-0.2869	0.0586	0.2083
Toluene	0.3699	0.1342	-0.3077	-0.0033	0.2523

The values of parameters, Z_{12} , Z_{21} , and a , b and c , have been calculated from their corresponding eqs. (10) and (11) and listed in Table 5. A perusal of this Table shows that the values differ appreciably from each other and are comparatively larger for those mixtures which involve strong interactions between the mixing components.

Experimental

All the organic liquids, viz. *n*-propylamine, acetone, ethyl alcohol, 1,4-dioxane, carbon tetrachloride, benzene

and toluene (all A.R. grade) were purified according to the standard procedures¹⁸. Their purities were checked by comparing their density and viscosity with those reported in literature¹⁹ at 303.15 ± 0.01 K, which almost agreed within the accuracy $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ g cm⁻³ and $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$ mPa.s respectively and are given in Table I. All the binary liquid mixtures were prepared in well-stoppered measuring flasks²⁰. The method of preparation of the binary liquid mixtures and other experimental details of the measurements of density and viscosity were the same as reported earlier²¹. The experimental values were in close agreement with the literature¹⁹. The reproducibility was better than $\pm 0.5\%$.

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